

CUSTOMER'S PREFERENCE TOWARDS ICE CREAMS

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Cite This Article: Dr. S. Selvendran, "Customer's Preference towards Ice Creams", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 3, Issue 1, Page Number 76-80, 2018.

Introduction:

At the stage of primitive economy, every individual, family or a social unit used to produce all that was necessary for their consumption. That means they were self-sufficient. Due to the advancement in science and technology more and more competitors emerged in the market with new variety of products. So it has become obligatory from the part of existing manufacture to maintain a cordial and satisfactory relationship with customers.

Customers:

Who will have certain expectations prior to the purchase known as customers. These expectations may be. Nature and performance of the product. The cost and efforts to be spent before obtaining the direct product or service benefits. The social benefits accruing to the customers as a result of the products.

Preference:

Preference is a kind of stepping away from the experience and evaluating it. One could have a pleasurable experience that caused dissatisfaction because even though pleasurable, it wasn't an emotion, it's the evaluation of an emotion.

History of Ice Creams:

The origin of ice cream can be traced back to at least the 4th century BC. Other early references include the Roman Emperor Nero (AD 37 – 68). Who ordered ice to be brought from the mountains and combined with fruit toppings and king tang (a 618 – 697) of sang, china. Who had a method of creating ice and milk concoction. Ice cream was likely bought from china back to Europe. Over time, receipts for ices, sherbets and milk ices evolved and served in the fashionable Italian and French royal courts.

After the desert was imported to the United States, it was served by several famous Americas including George Washington, Thomas Jefferson and Dolly Madison. In 1700, Governor Bladen of Maryland was recorded as having served it to his guests. In 1774 a London caterer named Philip Lenzi announced in New York news papers that he would be offering for sale various confections, including ice creams. The first ice cream parlor in America opened in New York in 1776. Augustus Jackson, a confectioner from Philadelphia, invented a recipes and method of marketing ice cream in 1832.

An England woman, Nancy Johnson invented a hand-cranked freezer in 1846 that established the basic method of marketing ice cream still used today. Johnson did not patent her own invention, however William G Young patented the "Johnson Patent Ice-Cream Freezer" in 1848.

In 1851, Jacob Frusseli in Baltimore established the first large-scale commercial ice cream plant. Alfred L Cralie patented an ice cream mold and disher on Feb 2, 1897. About 1926, the first commercially successful continuous process freezer was perfected and invented by Clarence Vogt.

Ice cream industry in India. The ice cream market growth picked up after de-reservation of the sector in 1997 of the total size of Rs 15 – 16 bn, around 30 – 32% is in the hands of the organized sector valued at Rs 4.9 bn, rest all is with the unorganized sector. Among the major players in this industry Hindustan Level has a market share of around 50% represented mainly by kwalkity walls brand. Amul with an estimated market share of 35% is rapidly gaining market share and lastly Vadilal is the player in the national market with 8 – 9% of the market share.

Ice cream market can be segmented in three different ways, namely on the basis of flavors, on the basis of stock keeping units / packing and on the basis of the customer segments. On the basis of the flavors the market has a number of flavors like vanilla, strawberry, chocolate, mango, butterscotch a number of fruit flavors dry fruit flavors, traditional flavors like kesar – pista, kanju – draksh etc. The market is totally dominated by vanilla, strawberry and chocolate, which together account for more than 70% of the market followed by butterscotch and other fruit flavors.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To know the customers preference towards ice cream.
- ✓ To know the brand of ice cream consumed by the sample respondents.

Source of Data:

The required data for this research obtained from the primary source and secondary source.

Primary Source of Data: Customer opinions regarding purchase and other related activities collected with the help of interview schedule.

Secondary Source of Data: History of the ice cream, ice cream industry position in India and other related information collected from the secondary source of data.

Research Design:

Sample Design: Convenience sampling technique used for collection of the required study units.

Sample Size: The researcher selected 50 customers as sample respondents.

Analysis:

Table 1: Age wise analysis

Age (in years)	Sample size	%
Below 10	03	06
10 – 20	33	66
21 & above	14	28
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 66% of the sample respondents are in the age group of 10-20 years.

Table 2: Gender wise analysis

Gender	Sample size	%
Male	13	26
Female	37	74
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 74% of the sample respondents are females.

Table 3: Educational qualification wise analysis

Educational Qualification	Sample Size	%
School	35	70
Technical	08	16
College	03	06
Others	04	08
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 70% of the sample respondents are educated up to school level.

Table 4: Marital status analysis

Marital Status	Sample Size	%
Married	04	08
Unmarried	56	92
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 92% of the sample respondent's marital status is unmarried.

Table 5: Occupation analysis

Occupation	Sample Size	%
Student	39	78
Workers	01	02
Employed	07	14
Business	03	06
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 66% of the sample respondents are in the age group of 10 – 20 years.

Table 6: Monthly Income Analysis

Monthly Income (in Rs)	Sample Size	%
Below 10,000	06	54.55
10,000 – 20,000	03	27.27
20,001 – 30,000	01	9.09
30,001 – and above	01	9.09
Total	11	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 54.55% of the sample respondents earn below Rs 10,000 as monthly income.

Table 7: Monthly budget for the purchase of ice cream

Monthly budget (in Rs)	Sample size	%
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Below 25	07	14
26 – 50	15	30
51 – 100	10	20
101 – and above	18	36
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 36% of the sample respondents spend Rs 101 – and above to purchase ice cream.

Table 8: Frequency of purchase of ice cream

Frequency of purchase	Sample size	%
Every week	22	44
Twice in a month	14	28
Once in a month	10	20
Others	04	08
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 44% of the sample respondents purchase ice cream once in a week.

Table 9: Liking the same type of ice cream

Liking the same type of ice cream	Sample size	%
Yes	17	34
No	33	66
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 66% of the sample respondents not like the same type of ice cream.

Table 10: Season of purchase analysis

Season of purchase	Sample size	%
Summer	20	40
Winter	16	32
Spring	02	04
All seasons	12	24
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 40% of the sample respondents buy ice cream during summer season.

Table 11: Time of purchase analysis

Time of purchase	Sample size	%
Morning	02	04
Afternoon	30	60
Evening	17	34
Night	01	02
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 60% of the sample respondents buy ice cream in afternoon.

Table 12: Point of purchase analysis

Point of purchase	Sample size	%
Ice cream parlor only	24	48
Sales vehicle only	07	14
Both	19	38
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 48 % of the sample respondents purchase ice cream at parlor only.

Table 13: Net weight of pack analysis

Net weight of pack	Sample size	%
Up to 25 gram	10	20
25 – 100 gram	22	44
101 – 150 gram	09	18
151 – gram and above	09	18

Total	50	100
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Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 44% of the sample respondents purchase ice cream in 25 – 100 gram pack.

Table 14: Quality of purchase during per visit analysis

Quality of purchase	Sample size	%
01	22	44
02 – 03	20	40
04	04	08
05 & above	04	08
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 44% of the sample respondents purchase one ice cream per visit.

Table 15: Brand mostly preferred analysis

Brand Mostly Preferred	Sample Size	%
Arun	23	46
Amul	08	16
Jamaai	16	32
Kwality	03	06
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 46% of the sample respondents purchase arun ice cream.

Table 16: Variety of ice cream mostly preferred analysis

Variety of ice cream mostly preferred	Sample size	%
Butter scotch	20	40
Vennila	11	22
Choco-bar	13	26
Strawberry	06	12
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 40% of the sample respondents purchase butter scotch variety of ice cream.

Table 17: Shape of ice cream mostly preferred analysis

Shape of ice cream mostly preferred	Sample size	%
Cup only	18	36
Stick only	03	06
Cone only	12	24
Any one	17	34
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 36% of the sample respondents prefer to purchase ice cream in cup only.

Table 18: Reason for linking of ice cream analysis

Reason for linking	Sample size	%
Color	23	46
Cheap	02	04
Taste	14	28
Others	11	22
Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, it is clear that 46% of the sample respondents buy ice cream because of attractive color.

Findings:

- ✓ Majority 66% of the sample respondents are in the age group of 10 – 20 years.
- ✓ Majority 74% of the sample respondents are females.
- ✓ Majority 70% of the sample respondents are educated up to school level.
- ✓ Majority 92% of the sample respondent's marital status is unmarried.
- ✓ Majority 66% of the sample respondents are in the age group of 10 – 20 years.
- ✓ Majority 54.55% of the sample respondents earn below Rs 10,000 as monthly income.

- ✓ Majority 36% of the sample respondents spend Rs 101 – and above to purchase ice cream.
- ✓ Majority 44% of the sample respondents purchase ice cream once in a week.
- ✓ Majority 66% of the sample respondents not like the same type of ice cream
- ✓ Majority 40% of the sample respondents buy ice cream during summer season.
- ✓ Majority 60% of the sample respondents buy ice cream in afternoon.
- ✓ Majority 48 % of the sample respondents purchase ice cream at parlor only.
- ✓ Majority 44% of the sample respondents purchase ice cream in 25 – 100 gram pack.
- ✓ Majority 44% of the sample respondents purchase one ice cream per visit
- ✓ Majority 46% of the sample respondents purchase arun ice cream.
- ✓ Majority 40% of the sample respondents purchase butter scotch variety of ice cream.
- ✓ Majority 36% of the sample respondents prefer to purchase ice cream in cup only.
- ✓ Majority 46% of the sample respondents buy ice cream because of attractive color.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Create awareness about demerits of the ice cream usage among the student by the school and parents this will leads to improve health of the children.
- ✓ Parents should cultivate saving habit among the children this will leads to save a part of monthly budget.

Conclusion:

Consumption of ice cream creates more employment opportunity in rural areas.

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